

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF "OFF-AXIS TENSION TEST" FOR UNIDIRECTIONAL
GRAPHITE-EPOXY COMPOSITES.

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ABSTRACT

The difficulty of finding correct values for the shear modulus G_{12} in fiber reinforced composites, due mainly to the restrained end effects is well known.

Several approaches proposed in the past included a correction factor to be applied on the apparent shear modulus, this factor being based on an analytical solution of a problem solved with other boundary conditions.

In this paper an approach also based on a correction factor is employed with two main characteristics. The specimen in the test is assumed to be rigidly clamped with no end rotations. The theoretical distributions of the mechanical values (stresses, strains and displacements), which permit evaluation of the correction factor, are calculated for the same configuration as that assumed for the test.

The distributions of stresses and strains are calculated numerically using the Finite Element Method. A parametric study has allowed a very simple correction procedure to be achieved for practical use, the key being in the independence of the correction factor on some properties of the material, for the value of the aspect ratio studied.

KEYWORDS : Shear Stiffness; Test Method; Intralaminar Failure; Finite Elements Analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

The determination of the intralaminar shear modulus G_{12} has been one of the main tasks as regards the experimental evaluation of the properties of fiber reinforced composites. Several tests have been proposed, all of them having serious drawbacks. Rail-shear test, thin walled tube torsion test, $\pm 45^\circ$ off-axis tension test, off-axis tension test and Iosipescu test can be mentioned among those more usually employed.

Two conditions must at least be fulfilled in an ideal test: the specimen

should be easy to prepare and a uniform and known distribution of the stresses along the ultimate fracture zone should be induced.

The off-axis tension test with a single orientation of the fibres fulfils some of the conditions previously enunciated for an ideal test. Moreover, if the fiber orientation angle with respect to the direction of application of the load is small ($\theta = 10^\circ$), high values of deformations can be reached before fracture, giving rise to a broad field of intralaminar shear modulus values.

However, it is well known that this test method involves some errors due to the influence of end constraints. Figure 1a represents the ideal deformed configuration of an off-axis specimen under traction. Figure 1b shows the deformed configuration but under complete rigid clamping with no end rotation, a situation which corresponds to a standard test. Obviously, this last problem does not have an analytical solution. Pagano and Halpin [1], solved the problem analytically with the displacement boundary conditions shown in Fig 1c, which cannot be simulated in a test machine. This solution has been used for many researchers as a basis to compare numerical and experimental values.

FIGURE 1. Schematic of several deformed configurations: a) No displacement restriction b) Rigid clamp without rotation c) Pagano and Halpin conditions.

Due to the significance of reference [1], it will be commented on in the next section, together with several approaches proposed to improve the values of the intralaminar shear modulus obtained in a test. Some incongruities found in subsequent papers, also discussed in the next section, will suggest a numerical analysis of the specimen which will be performed in section 3.

A parametric study, using the numerical model previously developed, will be performed at section 4 in order to investigate the solution dependency of the variables of the problem (longitudinal and transversal elasticity moduli, Poisson ratio, orientation angle of the fiber, etc.).

The applicability of the approach developed will be explained in section 5, and the paper will close with a brief discussion and the conclusions.

2.- STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Pagano and Halpin solved analytically the off-axis tension test specimen under boundary conditions at the midpoints of their ends, as in the scheme of Figure 1c. The solution obtained implies, of course, a certain distribution of displacements and tractions along these ends which cannot be reproduced in a test machine. With reference to the general configuration shown in Figure 2 the longitudinal stress and strain along the central line are:

$$\sigma_x(x,0) = C_2 \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon_x(x,0) = \bar{S}_{11} C_2 - \bar{S}_{16} C_0 h^2 \quad (2)$$

where:

$$C_0 = \frac{6\bar{S}_{16} \epsilon_0}{6h^2(\bar{S}_{11}\bar{S}_{66} - \bar{S}_{16}^2) + \bar{S}_{16}^2 L^2} \quad (3)$$

$$C_2 = \frac{C_0}{6\bar{S}_{16}} (6h^2\bar{S}_{66} + \bar{S}_{11}L^2) \quad (4)$$

\bar{S}_{ij} are the compliance coefficients with respect to the xy coordinate system, four of these being independent.

FIGURE 2. Specimen geometry.

The value E_x^* , taken as the apparent elasticity modulus in the x direction, is :

$$E_x^* = \frac{\sigma_x(x,0)}{\epsilon_x(x,0)} \quad (5)$$

which would be related to the true value $E_x (=1/\bar{S}_{11})$ in the following way:

$$E_x^* = E_x \frac{1}{1 - \eta(E_x)} \quad (6)$$

where $\eta(E_x)$ has the following expression:

$$\eta = \frac{6 \bar{S}_{16}}{\bar{S}_{11} (6 \bar{S}_{66} + \bar{S}_{11} \frac{L^2}{h^2})} \quad (7)$$

Pagano and Halpin indicate that η is a measure of the error, but of course when performing a test according to the boundary conditions indicated in Figure 1c, the value given by (5) was taken as the true value of E_x . The non consideration of this obvious fact has led to incorrect applications of correction factors based on the previous values of η .

Independently of the analytical study, Pagano and Halpin showed experimentally, using a nylon-reinforced rubber specimen, that the gripping restraint is a dominant factor in disturbing the uniform stress field.

Rizzo [2], performed a fairly complete numerical analysis modelling the conditions of Pagano and Halpin and also complete rigid clamping with and without end rotations. The study was developed for low values of the aspect ratio ($L/2h = 2, 4, 6$), trying to demonstrate the possibility of using no extremely long specimens. The results clearly showed, contradictorily to the experimental conclusion reached by Pagano and Halpin, that prevention of grip rotation was probably in itself a more adverse constraint than is rigid clamping. It could be deduced that using rotating grips, a drastic reduction in the error could be achieved calculating E_x as:

$$E_x = \sigma_{avg} / \epsilon_x \quad (8)$$

where σ_{avg} is the average nominal longitudinal stress and ϵ_x is the actual longitudinal strain (measured in a practical case using a strain gauge). This improvement would also affect the estimation of G_{12} , calculated using the general transformation equation:

$$\frac{1}{E_x} = \frac{1}{E_{11}} \cos^4 \theta + \left(\frac{1}{G_{12}} - \frac{2\nu_{12}}{E_{11}} \right) \cos^2 \theta \sin^2 \theta + \frac{1}{E_{22}} \sin^4 \theta \quad (9)$$

Chamis and Sinclair [3] proposed the ten degrees off-axis test for the determination of shear properties, based on the fact that τ_{12} was the major stress contribution to fracture determined from a combined-stress failure criterion. The configuration they proposed, however, had a very high aspect ratio (20 including tabs and slightly greater than 14 excluding them).

Pindera and Herakovich [4] showed some obvious facts overlooked by some researchers. The correct value of τ_{12} , the shear stress in the 1-2 coordinate system at the midpoint of the specimen is:

$$\tau_{12} = -\sigma_x \sin\theta \cos\theta + \tau_{xy} (\cos^2\theta - \sin^2\theta) \quad (10)$$

It was customary, in practice, to ignore the contribution of the shear stress τ_{xy} induced by the end constraints as well as the correct distribution of the tensile across the width of the specimen, giving rise to an approximate value of the shear stress, τ_{12}^* :

$$\tau_{12}^* = -\sigma_{xx} \sin\theta \cos\theta \quad (11)$$

Based on the analytical study of Pagano and Halpin, Pindera and Herakovich proposed the use of the following correction factor:

$$\frac{G_{12}}{G_{12}^*} = \frac{\tau_{12}}{\tau_{12}^*} = \frac{1 - \frac{\beta (\cos^2\theta - \sin^2\theta)}{\cos\theta \sin\theta}}{(1 - \frac{2}{3}\eta)} \quad (12)$$

where G_{12}^* , following the development of Pindera and Herakovich would be the result of dividing τ_{12}^* , according to (11), by the correct value of the strain deformation γ_{12} at the center of the specimen in the problem solved by Pagano and Halpin. Due to the fact that η depends in turn on G_{12} , an iterative procedure needs to be performed.

However, the approach proposed by Pindera and Herakovich takes, in practice, the value of γ_{12} as the one obtained from a test using rotating grips. This implies, conceptually, that a non-controlled error is introduced due to the fact that a correction factor based on certain boundary conditions is used to modify an incorrect solution obtained after some measures on a specimen under different boundary conditions.

Following this approach they performed several tests finding that, when the orientation angle is small, serious errors appear, both for G_{12}^* and for its corrected value according to (12), although significantly smaller in this case.

An immediate question arises. What is the reason for the poor accuracy of the results obtained for the values of G_{12}^* . According to the results of Rizzo (and confirmed by our numerical analysis), the use of rotating grips would imply very little perturbation for the configuration used by Pindera and Herakovich. In fact the values obtained by them are worse than those predicted by numerical analysis assuming clamped ends (as will be shown in the next section). This fact, together with the contradictory results obtained by Pagano and Halpin and by Rizzo, lead to the conclusion that either the numerical analysis does not reflect what is actually happening in a test or what is happening is not what is believed to happening.

Although outside of the area of interest of this paper, a precise analysis

of the correct conditions under which the completely rigid clamping with end rotation tests are performed would be required in order to clarify previous discrepant results and to gain insight into the practical effectiveness of such a device.

A second question (but no less important) is related to the possibility of correcting a value obtained through experimental measures with a factor based on the solution of a problem whose boundary conditions reproduce the real situation of the test.

Due to the impossibility of reaching such a solution analytically, it must be performed numerically, as will be developed in the next section. Believing that the situation in which a clearer correspondence between the test and the model can be achieved is complete rigid clamping with no end rotations (this device being, moreover, the immediate way to perform a tensile test) these will be the conditions reproduced in the following numerical study.

3.- NUMERICAL ANALYSIS.

A Finite Element analysis has been carried out on a specimen with the following characteristics, in order to compare with previous results.

$$L = 12.7 \text{ cm. ; } h = 0.635 \text{ cm. ; } t = 0.1905 \text{ cm.}$$

$$E_{11} = 136.6 \text{ GPa ; } E_{22} = 9.79 \text{ GPa ; } G_{12} = 4.998 \text{ GPa ; } \nu_{12} = 0.35$$

FIGURE 3. Finite Element discretization.

The discretization employed is depicted in Figure 3. 500 elements have been used, although finer discretizations have also been analyzed, no significant variations in the results being found. The results to be shown are obtained with a linear variation of the displacements along the boundary of each element (2D isoparametric solid, STIF42, ANSYS 4.3), although an alternative analysis including rotations as a variable at the nodes was also performed for comparison (8-node layered shell, STIF91, ANSYS 4.3). The errors observed between both alternatives were less than 0.4 %, the first being maintained due to its shorter computation time.

Some results are summarized in Table 1. γ_{12} and τ_{12} represent respectively the shear strain and stress at the center of the specimen. τ^*_{12} represents the value associated to (11), always calculated with

numerical results.

In order to examine further some of the questions presented in the previous section, results corresponding to several boundary conditions are included in Table 1 as well as the results of other authors.

TABLE 1 SOME RESULTS AFTER THE NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
$\gamma_{12} \times 10^{-3}$	2.43	2.43	2.678	2.48	2.68	2.634	---
τ_{12} (MPa)	12.169	12.169	13.389	12.403	13.410	13.169	---
τ^*_{12} (MPa)	13.810	13.810	13.362	14.244	13.362	13.645	---
$\tau^*_{12} / \gamma_{12}$ (GPa)	5.681	5.681	4.992	5.743	4.985	5.178	6.377

- (1) Pagano and Halpin analytical results.
- (2) Numerical solution modelling the condition of Pagano and Halpin.
- (3) Numerical solution with ideal boundary conditions allowing end rotations and transversal deformation.
- (4) Numerical solution modelling complete rigid clamping with no end rotations (according to Rizzo).
- (5) Id. allowing end rotations.
- (6) Numerical solution permitting rotation at one end.
- (7) Experimental values obtained by Pindera and Herakovich.

The second column has been included simply to check once again, after the satisfactory agreement with the results of the first column, the discretization employed. The comparison of the third, fourth and fifth columns support the idea that the differences due to the end constraints are mainly due to the prevention of end rotation. The sixth column has been included in an attempt to justify the neat (but contradictory according to the previous columns) experimental results shown by Pagano and Halpin. The results are intermediate between those corresponding to the two previous columns although closer to the fifth. Finally, the seventh column includes the experimental result obtained by Pindera and Herakovich. The value of G^*_{12} deduced by them has an error of 27.6% over the theoretical value. Correcting this value with the relation between τ_{12} and τ^*_{12} obtained from the first column this error is reduced to 12.4%. It must be observed that the value obtained by Pindera and Herakovich differs clearly from that predicted by the numerical value (assuming the experiment is performed without significant errors). With the boundary conditions employed by them the error should have been 0.35%. Even in the case of clamped ends, which are considered the worst conditions, the predicted error is 14.8%. The last two points discussed confirm the statement in the previous section about the need for a further study on the real situation of the grip allowing for rotation.

4.- PARAMETRIC STUDY.

The second question stated at the end of the second section can now be considered after the numerical solution. No errors, of course, in the final value of G_{12} would be reached if the apparent value obtained dividing τ_{12}^* by the shear measured deformation using a strain gauge rosette, was corrected by a factor deduced from a numerical analysis modelling the test conditions correctly. This is possible, but not practical from an engineering point of view. The only possibility is to investigate the dependence of G_{12}/G^*_{12} (or τ_{12}/τ^*_{12}) on the variables of the problem just in case it might be simple. The value of this relation depends on the aspect ratio ($L/2h$), the longitudinal elasticity modulus (E_{11}), the transversal elasticity modulus (E_{22}), the Poisson ratio (ν_{12}) and the fiber angle orientation (θ).

Maintaining the aspect ratio previously used, the variation of G_{12}/G^*_{12} versus γ_{12}/ϵ_0 is presented in Figure 4, always for rigid end clamping. The points represent the results of the numerical analysis for five different values of the shear modulus G_{12} (the same for the four angles considered) which acts as the external action.

The representation obtained suggests a linear dependence for the values of E_{11} , E_{22} , ν_{12} used. It must be noted that similar evolutions (linear, although slightly different) have also been found for the problem solved by Pagano and Halpin, although this fact was not apparent from the complicated analytical expressions that appear in ref [4].

FIGURE 4. Evolution of G_{12}/G^*_{12} versus γ_{12}/ϵ_0 for different fiber angle orientation for a given material.

The following steps must investigate the influence of the mechanical properties. Thus, the variation of the relation G_{12}/G^*_{12} versus E_{11} , E_{22} and ν_{12} for different fiber orientation angles will now be calculated. Figures 5, 6 and 7 show such variations.

FIGURE 5. Variation of G_{12}/G^*_{12} versus E_{11}

FIGURE 6. Variation of G_{12}/G^*_{12} versus E_{22}

FIGURE 7. Variation of G_{12}/G^*_{12} versus ν_{12}

It is clear from these Figures that the relation under consideration depends neither on the value of E_{22} nor on the value of ν_{12} . The relation is almost independent of E_{11} , a significant only variation appearing for a fiber orientation angle of 5° .

5.- PROPOSED APPROACH.

Due to the independence of the relation G_{12}/G^*_{12} versus ν_{12}/ϵ_0 with respect to the mechanical properties, only the dependence of the fiber angle orientation remains, for the aspect ratio considered in this paper. This suggests interpolating a straight line using the points represented in Figure 4. Using a minimum square approximation, the equations of these lines are:

$$\theta = 5^\circ \implies G_{12}/G^*_{12} = 0.95984 - 0.036444 (\nu_{12}/\epsilon_0)$$

$$\theta = 10^\circ \implies G_{12}/G^*_{12} = 1.00850 - 0.145200 (\nu_{12}/\epsilon_0)$$

$$\theta = 15^\circ \implies G_{12}/G^*_{12} = 0.96791 - 0.014122 (\nu_{12}/\epsilon_0)$$

$$\theta = 30^\circ \implies G_{12}/G^*_{12} = 1.00600 - 0.006706 (\nu_{12}/\epsilon_0)$$

These lines together with the points which have originated them are represented in Figure 8, now valid for a wide range of materials.

The value of the fiber orientation angle corresponding to 45° has not been represented, since it produces a horizontal line in the Figure.

The practical use of this curve is clear. A tensile test of a given material, the specimen having the aspect ratio-indicated, is performed. The specimen has to be instrumented in order to have strain gauge measures which make it possible to determine the value of ν_{12} . The test machine records the value of the applied force, which makes it possible to determine τ^*_{12} and hence G^*_{12} . Consequently the correct value of G_{12}

can be determined using the appropriate line of Figure 8.

FIGURE 8. Evolution of G_{12}/G^*_{12} versus γ_{12}/ϵ_0 for different fiber angle orientation.

6.- DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS.

An approach to correct the apparent value of the shear modulus obtained from a test has been proposed. The correction factor found is for the case of complete rigid clamping with no end rotation, on the grounds, firstly, that this is the normal situation in a test machine not requiring special devices and, secondly, that the correspondence between the test and the model is total, which does not seem to occur for other apparently more convenient configurations. This ensures that the correction factor that is going to be employed relates two situations with the same boundary conditions.

The key for a practical use of this proposal lies in the fact that the relation used to modify the apparent value of the shear modulus is not affected by the other mechanical properties of the materials, being linear for each value of the fiber orientation angle. When this angle is greater than 45° the numerical analysis performed indicates that no correction is needed, which is in concordance with the indications of other authors.

The previous conclusions are related to a particular aspect ratio widely studied in the literature. However, the extension of the approach to lower values of the aspect ratio seems to be necessary. The reason is that specimens as long as these are not always available. The proposed approach applied to a smaller aspect ratio will probably not lead to such a simple practical use as the one obtained for the aspect ratio studied. It is believed that the longitudinal elasticity modulus will have more influence when the boundary conditions more seriously affect the solution at the center of the specimen.

Finally, several experiments need to be carried out in order to

demonstrate the correctness of the hypothesis presented and the practical application of the proposed approach.

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7. REFERENCES.

- 1.- N. J. Pagano and J. C. Halpin, J. Comp. Mat., 2 (1), 18 (1968)
- 2.- R.R. Rizzo, J. Comp. Mat., 3, 202 (April 1969)
- 3.- C. C. Chamis and J. H. Sinclair, Exp. Mech., 17 (9), 339 (Sept. 1977)
- 4.- M. J. Pindera and C. T. Herakovich, Exp. Mech., 110 (March 1986)